

Identification of the Parameters of a AC Servomotor Using Genetic Algorithm

J. G. Batista, K. N. Sousa, J. L. Nunes, R. L. S. Sousa, G. A. P. Thé

Abstract—This work deals with parameter identification of permanent magnet motors, a class of ac motor which is particularly important in industrial automation due to characteristics like applications high performance, are very attractive for applications with limited space and reducing the need to eliminate because they have reduced size and volume and can operate in a wide speed range, without independent ventilation. By using experimental data and genetic algorithm we have been able to extract values for both the motor inductance and the electromechanical coupling constant, which are then compared to measured and/or expected values.

Keywords—Modeling, AC servomotor, Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor-PMSM, Genetic Algorithm, Vector Control, Robotic Manipulator, Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

POSITION control is essential for a wide range of industrial applications as, for instance, robotic manipulation, transportation in conveyor belts, etc., allowing for quality of products and processes as well as security. Typical choices for accomplishing motion in industrial application relied on the use of DC motors, a scenario which has changed due to the progresses carried out by power electronics in the development of frequency converters, thus opening the way for AC driving. Particularly important in this context was the advance of microelectronics, which provided frequency converters with increasingly complex functions [1].

Indeed, the use of electric motors with AC drives has increased significantly in recent years; main reasons for choosing motor/frequency converter assembly are speed adjustment, energy saving, position control and soft start, as well as adaptability to different motor technologies (synchronous, permanent magnet synchronous, switched reluctance, etc) [2].

A. The Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors

The Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors – PMSM, also called by the manufacturers of AC servo motor. "Booster" because this motor run with feedback monitoring system of the motor shaft due to a position sensor. The MSIPs fed by a frequency inverter can be used in industry where the speed variation with constant torque and high performance are

required [3]-[5].

The PMSM are also being used in applications where reliability, smooth torque, low vibration and noise are key [6].

The PMSM, generally used in applications where high performance is required, are very attractive for applications with limited space and reducing the need to eliminate because they have reduced size and volume and can operate in a wide speed range, without independent ventilation [7].

Following the market trends, the use of synchronous motors with permanent magnet is in wide expansion, also in the industry, because the motor has extra-high-yield, low volume and weight, smooth torque, low vibration and noise, wide band rotation with constant torque and with the advent from the 80s, Magnets Neodymium Iron Boron (NdFeB), high energy, there was an increase in the number of applications, which uses this technology [8].

B. The Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors AC

There are two main types of PMSM: DC and AC. The PMSM has the similar function with the DC motor with brushes. DC motor in the fixed magnetic field is formed by permanent magnets or coils that are in the stator. In the rotor are coils of armor where voltage and supply current to control speed and torque are applied. PMSM happens in reverse manner, we have a permanent magnet for generating the fixed field in the rotor and stator coils in which voltage to control speed and torque are applied.

In DC motor, torque control is realized by armature current. In PMSM, the torque control is accomplished through the vector or field oriented control. In this research we will use an AC PMSM drive for joint of a robotic manipulator SCARA (Selective Compliant Assembly Robot Arm) 4 degrees of freedom.

The aim of this paper is the identification of garments from PMSM for the lifting of transfer function, allowing subsequently control the motor using vector control for the movement of joints of the robotic manipulator mentioned above, since the robotic manipulator lies unused by problems the controller. The main idea in this moment would be the reuse of MSIPs that it is in perfect working order. For the motor drive a frequency inverter with vector control will be used.

The main justification for the application of this motor would be the high performance resulting in lower power consumption compared to other types of motors as well as other advantages mentioned above.

Josias G. Batista is with the SENAI, Fortaleza- CE, Brazil (phone: 55 08588315409; e-mail:josiasgb@yahoo.com.br).

Kleymilsondo N. Sousa and George A. P. Thé are with the UFC, Fortaleza - CE, Brazil (e-mail: kleymilson@gmail.com, geothe@hotmail.com).

José L. N. da Silva iswiththe IFCE, Limoeiro do Norte – CE, Brazil (e-mail: jleonardonunes@gmail.com)

Rigoberto L. S. Sousa iswiththe SENAI, Fortaleza- CE, Brazil(e-mail: rigoberto@edu.unifor.br).

II. VECTOR CONTROL

The vector control (also called Field Orientation Control - FOC) is a method used in variable speed drive for AC PMSM to control the torque, and hence, the speed, through a control loop that monitors the current sent to the machine.

Vector control allows achieving a high degree of accuracy and speed in the torque and speed control.

The motors vector control can be further divided into two types: normal and "sensorless" (without sensors). Recently, many researches are conducted for the control of PMSM using vector control. The idea is to estimate the rotor position through angle estimation, where the stator voltages and currents signals are used to estimate the instantaneous flow. The position value is obtained through the phase angle of the stator current which can be controlled to keep it perpendicular to the rotor magnetic field vector for excellent range of torque and speed [9].

With the advent of permanent materials (PM) with high coactivity of residual flow, it has been possible for the PMSM are higher than the induction of general use in power density, ratio of torque to inertia, and efficiency of motors. Therefore, PMSM are most interest in many industrial applications as substitutes for induction motors. Furthermore, the vector control MSIPs is much simpler than that the induction motor because there is no need to consider the slip frequency as in the induction motor [6]. However, a vector control of PMSM requires a position sensor, to correctly orient the current vector orthogonal to the flow, since the rotor flux is obtained from permanent magnets. Thus, we can directly control the torque simply acting on the amplitude of stator current. Thus, one can achieve a high degree of torque control of wide speed range, including motor braking, which can be instantly [7].

Fig. 1 illustrates the representation of the electrical equivalent circuit of the PMSM per phase. We can observe that the DC motor is similar, except that the values of current and voltage are sinusoidal [3], [4].

Fig. 1 Electrical equivalent circuit of the PMSM

The vector control of PMSM allows current phase remains in phase with the electromotive force against (BEMF) all the time and controlling the amplitude of the phase current can adjust the motor torque.

Fig. 2 shows the relationship of voltage vectors of the electric circuit shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2 Voltage Vectors of the PMSM

Since the voltage vectors can be concluded:

$$V_{un} = \sqrt{(V_L)^2 + (E_G + V_R)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{un} = \sqrt{(2\pi f_e L I_U)^2 + (k_{E\phi} n_M + I_U R)^2} \quad (2)$$

where n_M is the rotation speed of the motor, f_e is the frequency of the rotating field of rotor, R is the coil resistance per phase, L is coil inductance per phase, I_U is current phase and $k_{e\phi}$ is a constant that depends on the constructive characteristics of motor.

The current cannot be isolated, because it has non-linear dependence parameters:

$$I_u = f(V_{un}, n_M) \quad (3)$$

We also have that:

$$\tau = k_T \cdot I_U \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3 shows the block diagram of the PMSM:

Fig. 3 Block diagram of the PMSM

where: J_{total} is the moment of inertia of the mechanical system: the motor shaft more load; B is the viscous friction; K_T is the torque constant.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The experiment was conducted in the laboratory using a brushless motor whose characteristics are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 BRUSHLESS MOTOR DATA

Number of poles	2
Resistance (R) per phase	10 Ω
Potency (P)	160 W
Voltage (V)	220Vca
Frequency (f)	60 Hz
Rated Torque(T_{nom})	$9.55*(P_r/N_r) = 9.55*(160/3000) = 0.5094$ Nm

For identifying the parameters, the experiment illustrated in Fig. 4 was performed data were collected and are shown in Table II.

Fig. 4 Scheme of the experiment to identify the parameters

In this experiment, we used an AC-DC-AC converter (variable frequency drive) applying modulated PWM voltage.

This inverter has the option to open-loop vector control, sensorless. Fig. 5 shows the diagram of the frequency inverter used in PMSM drive.

Fig. 5 Diagram of the frequency inverter used in the PMSM drive

Fifteen tests conducted by varying the frequency at 5 Hz, the current values corresponding to a phase were measured using a current clamp ammeter. Phase voltage was obtained by measuring the inverter output were measured.

The values of rotations were obtained using a tachometer with laser optical measurement.

TABLE II
 VALUES OBTAINED IN THE TEST WITH PMSM

Test	I (A)	U(V)	f (Hz)	Rotation(rpm)
01	0.6	15	5	150
02	0.8	18	10	300
03	0.9	24	15	450
04	1.1	31	20	630
05	1.0	36	25	770
06	0.9	40	30	910
07	0.8	45	35	1060
08	0.8	50	40	1210
09	0.7	55	45	1360
10	0.6	60	50	1509
11	0.6	64	55	1659
12	0.5	68	60	1809
13	0.3	69	65	1960
14	0.8	70	70	2135
15	0.8	72	75	2276

IV. GENETIC ALGORITHM – GA

Genetic algorithms are especially used to find solution of problems with a large search space, with many restrictions and problems with several parameters with a high possibility of combinations [10]. This applies to the problem in question, because there must be a pair (K, L) such that, if applied to (2) provides solution for all test data presented in Table II.

The idea to use Genetic Algorithm (GA) is that it is able to evolve a population of candidate solutions to a given problem, so that an operator inspired by natural genetic variation and natural selection will find best solution [10]. Fig. 6 summarizes the process, and chooses the best solution. We used the GA in this work because it was the method that is currently available faster.

Fig. 6 Steps to implement the GA

Each individual in the population, which is random

initialized, has 24 bits as shown in Fig. 7 and this figure consists of the input parameters.

Fig. 7 Individual or chromosome formed by 24 bits

Each individual generates a solution of voltage according to (2) that seeks to satisfy the measurement of voltage tests. From this it will be reported as the best individual evolves along the search, the term best guy who has lower cost (fitness). Individuals with the best reviews will be selected to generate new individuals, thus formed a new generation of solutions [11].

When generating a set of (population) solutions using genetic algorithm, these results are evaluated individually, receiving a score according to the need and constraints imposed by the project. To make this assessment, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) uses an equation fitness (5), calculated for the entire range of frequencies tested, and associates a note. The evolution of the evaluation of best individual is shown in Fig. 8.

$$Rating = \sum | (Test\ Result - Result\ AG) | \quad (5)$$

In this research, several trials, we was observed that after generation 500 there are almost no change in the best individual, in this way, the problem in question, the stopping criterion was chosen number of generations equal to 1000. We can be seen in Fig. 8 that this generation number meets the needs of search.

Fig. 8 Evaluation of the Evolution of Best Individual (solution) using GA

Another consideration in the algorithm is that there is elitism, in other words the best individual always remains in the next generation, this is a way not to lose the best solution if it has already been found[10].

V. ANALYSIS OF RESULTS OF IDENTIFICATION WITH GA

Simulating the algorithm using GA for multiple tests with different voltages and frequencies, we found as the best solution values as Table III.

TABLE III
 BEST PARAMETERS FOUND BY THE GA

Parameter Searched	Best results found
L (Inductance)	26.50 mH
K (Motor constant)	0.149 V/rad/s

The value found for the inductance is compatible with the same type motors and with equivalent specifications. For comparison, the CMP40S motor manufacturer SEW EURODRIVE [12] presents rated speed equal to 3000 rpm (same as indicated on the motor nameplate in research), rated torque of 0.5 Nm (comparable to the calculation of Table I) , per phase resistance of about 10 ohms (also comparable to the motor test), equal to inductance and 23.0 mH.

It is worth mentioning that, during the analysis of the results of Genetic Algorithm, we supposed that the inductance has less influence in obtaining lower of cost function of the constant K. The values presented in Table III correspond to approach the order of 1.2 V between the measured voltage value (Table II) and the theoretical value of convergence voltage obtained via the genetic algorithm. This is in the range from 2.0 to 4.0% for intermediate values of frequency, which is acceptable if the measurement process uncertainties are taken into account.

Although the inductance could be measured with equipment such as FLUKE - AM 6304 - PROGRAMMABLE AUTOMATIC METER RLC, the absence of such equipment in the laboratory and a procedure for estimating K justify, in the opinion of the authors, the adoption of the method used.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The adoption of the electrical equivalent circuit of the PMSM reveals a mesh equation (2), which relates the physical parameters of motor (U, K, R, number of pair of poles, etc.) with the excitation parameters (voltage and current). Through the tests we were able to find the mechanical parameters of motor. From the viewpoint of the dynamic model of said motor has been possible to construct the transfer function.

In this study, the approach of genetic algorithms to find a solution for the unknowns L (inductance) and K (electromechanical coupling) showed a method of rapid convergence (only 500 generations) were extracted by means of which $L = 26, 5 \text{ mH}$ and $K = 0.149 \text{ V / rad / s}$ for the frequency range of 75 Hz is not to say that the method used was the best because there are several methods that could be used. Particularly, the inductance value obtained is comparable to similar motors as well as parameters related to the mechanics. To tests performed to found here the transfer function of the motor researched. The main idea of this work is to find the transfer function of the motor control to perform this motor.

As future research, the motor control to drive a robotic

SCARA manipulator that uses this motor in the joints, the dynamic model of the manipulator and finally the development of the controller will be held.

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Josias G. Batista holds a degree in Electromechanical Technology Education Center at Ceará (2003) and graduate *Latu Sense* in Industrial Automation from the University of Fortaleza (2008). Currently doing Masters in EngTeleinformatics the Federal University of Ceará and develops research activities in industrial control and robotics.

Kleymilson do N Sousa was born in Fortaleza - Ceará, Brazil. Graduated in Mechatronics at Technological Education Center of Ceará (2006) and MSc in Electrical Engineering from the Federal University of Ceará - UFC (2012) and currently Doctoral makes the UFC, plus study develops the Group's Research Laboratory of Energy Efficiency and Driving Machine - (LAMOTRIZ). The main areas of research focus on neural networks, genetic algorithms, artificial intelligence and designs of transformers and motors.

José L. N. da Silva holds a degree in Electromechanical Technology by CENTEC Institute (2005), postgraduate Industrial Automation University of Fortaleza-UNIFOR (2008) and a degree in Vocational Education from the University of Southern Santa Catarina UNISUL (2010). Acts as a consultant and trainer in the areas of Senai Industrial Automation, Industrial Robotics and retrofitting of machines and equipment.

Rigoberto L. S. Sousa holds a degree in Electromechanical Technologist in the Center of Technological Education Institute (2002) and expertise in Industrial Automation, University of Fortaleza (2008). Higher Education is currently Instructor-SENAI-Regional Department of Ceará. Has experience in Electrical Engineering with emphasis in Electrical and Electronics and Automation.

George A. P. Thé holds a degree in Electrical Engineering (2005) and MSc in Teleinformatics Engineering (2006), both from the Federal University of Ceará and a doctorate in electronic Engineering at Politecnico di Torino (2010). He is a professor at the Federal University of Ceará and currently develops research activities in electronic instrumentation and modeling for industrial applications.